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MARKETING MANAGEMENT OF SMALL SCALE INDUSTRIES IN VARANASI DISTRICT

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Abstract

Varanasi, or Benares, (also known as Kashi) is one of the ancient cities in the world. The word 'Kashi' has emerged from the word 'Kas' which means to shine, depicting our tradition and mythological legacy. Kashi is the 'original ground' created by Shiva and Parvati, upon which they stood at the beginning of time. Apart from offering breathtaking scenic beauties of ghats across the Ganges, it has been the epitome of traditional classical culture, glorified by myth and legend and sanctified by religion; magnetizing a host of pilgrims and worshippers.

Varanasi has, since times immemorial, been hailed as a premier centre for some of the finest handicrafts. The most renowned craft of the city is silk weaving. 'Baranasi Sarees' produced by local craftsman are among the most preferred, not only in India but across the world. Brassware, copperware, ivory work, glass bangles, wood and clay toys and exquisite gold jewellery are some of the other crafts the city is famous for. Bhadohi Carpets and musical instruments are among the other shopping attractions.

In the present paper, an attempt has been made to throw light on the marketing practices(i.e. the four P's of product price place and promotion around which all the marketing activities revolve for satisfying the needs and wants of the consumers.) being followed by the entrepreneurs of Small Scale Industries engaged in the Varanasi District and for the above purpose the primary data has been gathered from survey conducted among the entrepreneurs who are engaged in the nineteen most prominent industries of Varanasi.

Key words: socio –economic development, Small Scale Industries, entrepreneurship

Introduction

Small Scale Industries acts as a catalyst in the socio –economic development of India as it facilitates in tapping of resources for judicious use with low capital investment in reducing regional disparities, generating employment opportunities and increasing exports by fostering entrepreneurship

Methodology

The present study is analytical and descriptive in nature, and is divided into two parts. First section analyses the marketing practices which are being followed by the entrepreneurs of the Small Scale Industries by conducting a survey among them and the second section is devoted for studying their potentials, problems and prospects.

Section -I

Features of SSI in Varanasi

Varanasi has been an important centre for SSIs in India .The industries in Varanasi has certain features. First, the SSIs in Varanasi comprises, Banarasi Saree, power loom saree, embroidery, saree printing, ready garments , hosiery , food , wood , chemicals engineering , zaree , glass beads, enamelling , zarda surti , carpet printing press. Second most of the entrepreneurs engaged in these industries have basically a parental tradition of the industries .Third normally the entrepreneurs don't possess formal education in the area of marketing .Further the industries are dominated by sole proprietorship followed by partnership , firms , cooperative and company form of organization. Those entrepreneurs who have set up a company form of organization. Those entrepreneurs who have set up company form of organization .Those entrepreneurs who have set up a company form of organization preferred the structure of private limited companies. Sixthly, these industries are male dominated. Seventh, of the total units registered with the appropriate authority, half of them met with immature deaths. The prominent areas responsible for their extinction are non-availability of expected raw materials, inadequate working capital insufficient infrastructural facilities and other environmental hazards. Persons belonging to different religions are engaged in these industries.

1. Marketing planning and organization

During the course of survey, researcher has observed that the entrepreneurs engaged in the SSI in Varanasi are very much aware about the role of marketing planning. However, they are of the opinion that it is much more essential for big business than the small ones. Though they lack appropriate training and proper understanding of formulating their marketing plan. In fact, none of the SSI units operating in Varanasi possess any written statement of marketing plan. However, they keep in mind market conditions, nature of demand, level of competition, availability of raw materials etc. While planning to decide quality of product, appropriate final price, the type of buyers also may purchase the products and the market where their products and the market where the products would be offered for sale. They rely much more for short term plan. It had further been experienced that the entrepreneurs are very much aware of the changing pattern of environmental forces. Though they are aware of their strengths and weakness they don't have well thought programme to remove the weakness and face the challenges. However, they try to consolidate their strengths by satisfying their supplier and distributor. At times they appeal to the government for suitable actions .It may further be noted that the SSIs don't set their marketing objectives on the basis of organizational objectives, nor do they have written statements about

marketing objectives, but they select their target market for marketing their products. Basically, the SSIs sell their major parts of production in local markets. However, only a small number of saree printing units, hosiery units food product units, enamellings units and wood units sell their products in the regional markets. Similarly , only a few power loom saree units manufacture, Banarasi sarees obviously have to concentrate on the needs and wants of women belonging to different income groups and residing in urban , sub-urban and rural areas .In brief age , gender , income , location , lifestyle, occasion education , customer attitude, occupations, lifestyle occasion, education, interest and hobbies , religion and benefit sought are the major variables on the basis of which the entrepreneurs segment their market .It is that they don't carry out at systematic and scientific marketing research for gathering valuable information rather they rely on past experience or intuition or hunch. Regarding selling product in the market every marketer has to formulate his marketing mix strategy. The SSI units operating in Varanasi district also develop their marketing mixes, product decisions occupies the first place followed by the pricing decisions , distribution decisions and promotion decisions .In all almost all industries the maximum emphasis is being placed on product decisions as they lack well formulated set of marketing objectives , they also lack effective and systematic marketing organization. It appears that they organize their marketing activities in tune with the prevailing situation. Of course, the entrepreneurs need to realize the value of organizing marketing objectives in tune with the prevailing situation. The entrepreneurs are very much concerned with the production activities and therefore, it may be concluded that they are guided by production oriented philosophy of the business rather than marketing oriented approach.

2. Product policies and practices

Product is the first and the most important element of the marketing mix because each and every marketing decision begins with the decisions regarding product, and the level of customers' satisfaction and organizational goal achievement is measured in terms of product performance in the market, as it acts as a competitive weapon and when it is not handled properly it becomes a vehicle of corporate collapse and customers dissonance. Products offered by the Small Scale units in Varanasi are physical products having some colour and design, quality and performance, branding and packaging, prioriting sellers service. Though the SSIs operating in Varanasi are not guided absolutely by the modern marketing philosophy, they develop their product strategy basically on traditional basis, their product strategies are developed with a view to increasing sales and attracting and holding customers by meeting their expectations. There are few units within power loom and engineering industry which keep in mind the use of new and better raw materials and process while designing their product strategies .These industrial units decide their product policies with regard to product items, product line, product mix, and product diversification, colour, design quality etc. These decisions vary from one SSIs to another.

Our study reveals that SSIs in Varanasi are very much aware of the socio –psychological cultured and religious values of colour. Now a day's modern chemicals and dyes are used. So far as the creation of designed is concerned, these units don't face any serious problems because most of them get their designs developed with the help of computer. The use of brand names is not very popular in the small scale units operating in Varanasi. In recent years few industrial units have started using packaging so as to attract the customers. It is significant to note that in recent years the SSI units have recognized the value of design, colour combination and the use of materials in the branding and packaging .This further shows that the products of the SSI units are being modified , redesigned and restructured on the basis of market demand and availability of raw materials .However ,the units are not very much aware about the different stages of the Product Life Cycle and their role in marketing , financial soundness , market coverage and the degree of intensity for developing the products. Of course in this new millennium, they have to face unknown challenges anywhere, everywhere initially at product front, this calls for adopting modern tools and techniques of product policies and practices for satisfying target market and earning a satisfactory level of profit. The entrepreneurs engaged in the SSI have to develop a sound product strategy

in order to satisfy the customers in a better way. The entrepreneurs may take short term training in the fields of marketing. They may also visit different websites on a small fee for getting required theoretical guidelines for designing effective and persuasive product strategy.

3. Pricing Policies and Practices

The entrepreneur engaged in Varanasi determine the prices of their product with a view to obtaining the target rate of return on investment , sales growth , maximizing profits , meeting or preventing competition, stabilizing prices and increasing market share. While setting the price the entrepreneurs consciously keep in mind the internal and external environment forces. We have observed that the entrepreneurs are fully aware that they have to face tough competition with modern industries which are equipped in the sufficient market information and marketing resources .They are also aware that now the customers are educated have more information and have become choosy .Apart from these they invariably consider marketing objectives, cost of production, length of channels of distribution and promotion policies as also the image of the product in the market. However, the entrepreneurs don't normally consider the stages of product units life cycle for deciding the price.

It has been inferred during our course of survey that normally cost plus pricing, competitive parity pricing, demand oriented pricing are adopted by the sample units .Of them ,cost plus pricing occupies the prime place followed by competition oriented pricing and demand oriented pricing . The entrepreneurs carefully by observing the market situation change the prices of their products. There are two important pricing policies which are normally followed by entrepreneurs, one price policy and variable price policy. On an average 70% of the respondents follow variable pricing policy, while the rest adopt one price policy. Further the SSI units operating in Varanasi, different discounts are also prevailing such as quantity discounts, cash discounts and seasonal discounts. These discounts vary from one industry to another, but the promotional discounts and special discount are not very much in use. They don't commonly don't sell their products directly to ultimate customers; instead their products are sold by using different channel members. As a result, discounts are given to the channel members mainly for the purpose of prompt payment .The SSI operating in Varanasi are also very much conscious at least of their decisions , if not so for other elements of marketing. These units also resort to price changes. Their products have varying demand patterns While saree industry, embroidery , zaree and printed saree have rigorous seasonal demand readymade garments , hosiery , food products and glass beads have virtually regular demand, but these industries face tough competition with modern large scale industries which make their demand pattern flattering. These industries always try to keep their prices stable. The factors which are responsible for changes in price are competitive pressures; declining sales are the most significant reasons for the change in price.

The levels at which pricing decisions are made different from one industry to another and from one ownership pattern to another .In a proprietorship concern; it is the proprietors who take each and every decision regarding the operation and management of the concern including marketing decisions. In a partnership concerns these decisions are taken by the partners in a collective manner.

4. Channels of Distribution

The researcher has analyzed that SSIs under different industry located in Varanasi keep in mind their channel objectives .Normally ensuring quick sales at low cost, minimizing the level of inventory of finished goods , maintaining the quality of product in transit and ensuring greater protection and safety one of the major channel objectives of a large number of small scale units .Further, there are a few units small in size , believe in quick disposal of the product at a profit as the ultimate goal of the channels of distribution. The channel objectives like market intelligence and market control have still to carve out a

place in the channel objectives of the small scale units. While choosing, the marketing channels, the sample units take into consideration several factors of them channel objectives, market features, product attributes, price promotion trade policies and practices are important. They sell their products through their traditional channels. It appears they are not willing to use innovative channels or they don't seriously consider the reorganization of their distribution system. The factors which are taken into consideration by the sample units for selecting the mode of transportation are availability of transport , suitability , reliability cost, buyer's preference and time consumption of these costs of transportation ,time taken by the transport companies and availability of transport , time taken by the transport companies and availability of transport are very important. The units under Banarase saree, power loom saree, embroidery, saree printing, food chemicals, engineering, and enamellings are very much depending on the services of the middlemen.

Finally, it may be concluded that the Channel of Distribution existing at present in the Small Scale Industries are not going to strengthen these industries in the present market conditions

5. Promotion policies and Practices

The SSI operating in Varanasi district doesn't have aggressive promotion strategies. They normally make efforts to minimize the confidence of channel members for selling their products and therefore it may be concluded that they virtually use push strategy. However, they also use pull strategy sporadically. All the units decide their promotion budget on the basis of their capacity to expand .Whatever, promotion activities the SSI undertake, they are undertaken through internal organization.

Our study reveals that the SSI for the purpose of promoting their products rely more on Personal Selling than on advertising and sales promotion .By its very nature publicity is not directly carried out by the Small Scale units themselves. Advertising is used in a very limited manner; the same is true about sales promotion. More importantly , the Banarasi saree units , power loom saree units embroidery units , woods , glass beads units and enameling units the services of professional sales person are not all used.

Though advertising is a potent and dynamic tool of promotion and it is not being considered very significant by the sample small scale units .It can be inferred that out of the total amount survey 84% of the units don't prefer to use different media of advertising .Only about 16% of the units go for advertising those who take the help of advertising advertise locally. It is also evident that none of the Small Scale units advertise their products either at the national and international level. The major constraints standing in the way of advertising are limited resources, satisfactory sales trend and increased cost of promotion. It was further deduced that though sales promotion is an incentive to buy, it lacks popularity and attractiveness in Small Scale Industries operating in Varanasi .Out of the thirteen sample SSIs the proportion of the non-users is three times high as against the users. In particular , embroidery , hosiery and zaree industries don't take the help of sales promotion for enhancing the sales .However ,sales promotion technique are very much popular in enameling industry followed by chemicals and power loom .It is thus obvious that a large number of SSIs prefer to keep themselves isolated from the job of sales promotion, limited resources and scope and high cost are the two major reasons for not using any sales promotion except taking part in trade fairs and exhibitions followed by special discounts .

Section -II

Potentials of SSI

The SSI located in Varanasi possess high potential their potentialities can be assessed on the basis of the locational situation of the units availability of the means of transport and communication, flow of foreign tourist , availability of power , availability of labour force ,nearness to different market areas ,facilities of entrepreneurial shoulders , nearness to go to institution or agencies , availability of different banks and financial institutions etc.

Prospects of SSI

The SSI in India including the industries operating in Varanasi has a very good prospect. As a matter of fact, the prospects of any industry rests on the size of market , the nature and pattern of demand , customer's attitude and behavior , economic conditions of individual customers , cost of manufacturing a large number of products items of varied quantities , sizes , designs etc.It means each and every segment of SSI act as the product manufactured by the SSIs can be marketed not only in foreign countries but in domestic market also.

Now a days, with rise in literacy rate, the industries may get educated worker who can be trained for performing specific job easily .There are several government schemes aimed at upgrading expanding and diversifying the small scale industrial units in the country not only for generating revenue to the unit and employment to the society but also for enhancing foreign exchange earnings of the country.

Problems of SSI

Though the SSIs in India in general and UP in particular is capable of expanding and diversifying the products ranging from low to high quality products as such they have been facing a lot of serious attention because of the fact that the industries by nature are ill-organized, ill equipped, ill -informed and incapable of establishing effective link with the market.

• Production Problems

Small Scale units are often faced with the problems associated with production. The predominant factors that hamper the production process is the non-availability of suitable machinery suppliers, lack of sound production planning and control system, technological obsolescence , inability to upgrade the technology , scarcity of raw materials , improper layout , high cost of inputs , lack of research and development set up are the other problems that adversely affect not only the production but also upset the cost of production as well as the quality of finished products.

• Financial Problems

The scarcity of credit and finance is the major obstacle in the development of SSI units. The non-availability of adequate amount of credit and finance from the banks and financial institution create a situation of financial crisis in the small scale sector and forces the small entrepreneurs to rely on other sources like leader who charge an exorbitant rates of interest. This high cost of capital results in the high cost of final products and also leads to escalation in the cost of project. Besides there is a wide gap between sanctioned and disbursement by the commercial bank to the small scale sector, considerable delay can be observed.

• Personnel Problems

With a view to ascertain the personnel problems of the sample SSIs an opinion survey conducted by the researcher. Through the survey it has been inferred that SSI have several problems with regard to personnel, such as lack of effective personnel planning and policies, lack of skilled labour, problem of child labour, level of awareness of the labour laws of the country, lack of training facilities at unit level, lack of reliable work force and intra –industry rivalry relating to skilled workers. Around 90% units face the problems of skilled labour absence of suitable personnel planning and policies, lack of reliable labour force and intra industry, rivalry with regard to skilled workers.

- **Marketing Problems**

None of the units have expressed the view that the product quality, the designs, the price, the channel members, the promotional techniques of other units are the major competitive factors for them. Perhaps the Small Scale units consider the industry as their competitors and competition not as the marketing problem.

Assisting the SSI to improving the Global Competitiveness

Keeping in view the ensuring threats and challenges for the SSIs, the government has initiated several steps to improve the health of SSIs so that it could face with great vigor and zeal global competition. The major steps are as under.

- Technological up gradation
- Infrastructural assistance through the cluster approach.
- Availability of credit in time.
- Adoption of modern management and practices.
- Use of electronic infrastructure marketing and timely information dissemination

Conclusion

The greatest problem which these units face some years now is in the area of marketing. The units face stiff competition from large units. Therefore, more concentrated efforts particularly in the area of marketing are required. On the part of the government entrepreneurs promotional agencies and financial agencies, so that the growth rate of SSI sector can be accelerated further. In spite of such weaknesses no one can ignore the fact that the SSI sector has been playing a very significant and strategic role in India's capital scarce and a labour abundant economy of continental dimensions. For the rapid and healthy industrialization of the economy what is needed is a mixture of both small and large scale sector." the future development of SSIs must be seen as complementary to industry and large scale industry.

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